

EFFECTS OF GAGE LENGTH AND LOADING RATES ON THE STRENGTH OF PPTA FIBERS

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1 Introduction

Axial tension and transverse compression experiments on single fibers were performed to investigate the mechanical behavior of three high-performance fibers (Kevlar[®], Kevlar[®] 129, and Twaron[®]) with diameters in the order of 9~12 μm . The single fibers were manufactured from 1998 through 2008. A miniaturized tensile Kolsky bar [1, 2] was used to determine the tensile response of PPTA single fibers at a high strain rate. Gage length and strain rate were found to have minimum effects on the tensile strength of PPTA single fibers [3]. Manufacturing time over a decade was found to have negligible effects on the tensile strength of the fibers.

2 Experimental Results and Discussion

2.1 Materials

Three different types of high performance single PPTA fibers are chosen for the experimental study; Kevlar[®], Kevlar[®] 129, and Twaron[®] fibers. Single Kevlar[®] and Twaron[®] fibers are carefully extracted from yarns in both warp and weft (fill) directions from a woven fabric. The Kevlar[®] 129 fibers are taken from a yarn that has not gone through a weaving process. A single fiber with 9~12 μm diameter is nominally considered round and uniform.

2.2 Quasi-Static Experiments

The quasi static longitudinal tensile experiments are performed according to the ASTM standard test method for tensile strength and Young's modulus of fibers (C1577-03) with a hydraulically driven MTS810 machine at a constant crosshead speeds. The longitudinal Young's modulus E_3 of Kevlar[®], Kevlar[®] 129, and Twaron[®] single fibers are measured to be 109.39 ± 5.45 GPa, 108.98 ± 3.40 GPa, and

152.49 ± 9.22 GPa with 95% confidence interval from the results of fifteen repeated tests on each type of fiber. The ultimate strengths of Kevlar[®], Kevlar[®] 129, and Twaron[®] single fibers are measured to be 4.83 ± 0.29 GPa, 4.40 ± 0.16 GPa, and 4.74 ± 0.32 GPa, respectively. To study the gage-length effects on the PPTA single fibers studied in this research, in addition to the tensile experiments at a gage length of 10 mm, quasi-static tensile experiments are also performed at five other different gage lengths of 2.5, 5.5, 50, 100, and 250 mm. Figure 1 shows the variations of the ultimate strengths of the Kevlar[®] and Twaron[®] single fibers over the gage length range. The experimental results show that the effect of the gage length on the tensile strengths of these fibers is insignificant as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig.1. Variation of the ultimate strength of PPTA single fibers over the gage length.

2.3 High Strain Rate Experiments

In order to determine the tensile response of high performance single fiber at high rates, we modified a Kolsky tension bar, also called a split Hopkinson tension bar (SHTB) for single-fiber tests. A photograph of a miniature tension bar for a single-

fiber test at high strain rate is shown in Fig. 2. The miniature tension bar we used consists of an incident bar with a flange, a fiber specimen, and a load cell. The gage length of the fiber specimen is limited to the 2 mm to achieve an early dynamic force equilibrium state in the fiber during deformation. The strain rate ($\dot{\epsilon}$) in the fiber specimen is calculated using the following equation:

$$\dot{\epsilon} = -\frac{v}{l_s} = \frac{c_0}{l_s} (\epsilon_i - \epsilon_r) \quad (1)$$

where v is the particle velocity at the end of the incident bar, l_s is the length of the specimen, c_0 is the elastic bar wave speed in the rod, and ϵ_i and ϵ_r are the incident and reflected strains respectively. By integration, we obtain the strain in the fiber specimen as a function of time t .

$$\epsilon = \int_0^t \frac{c_0}{l_s} [\epsilon_i(\tau) - \epsilon_r(\tau)] d\tau \quad (2)$$

Fig.2. A photograph of miniature tension bar for single fiber tests at high strain rate.

In order to examine the strain-rate effects on the tensile failure strength of the PPTA single fibers, we performed tensile experiments at three strain rates: 0.001, 1, and 1500 s^{-1} . Figure 3 shows the tensile strength distribution of PPTA single fibers as a function of strain rates. As shown in Fig. 3 the experimental results of Kevlar[®] and Twaron[®] single fibers do not show significant strain-rate effects on tensile strength within the strain-rate range from $\dot{\epsilon} \approx 0.001s^{-1}$ to $\dot{\epsilon} \approx 1500s^{-1}$. The mechanical behavior of three high performance PPTA single

Fig.3. Variation of the ultimate strength of PPTA single fibers over strain rates.

fibers (Kevlar[®], Kevlar[®] 129, and Twaron[®]) was studied at both quasi-static and high strain rates. The failure strengths of Kevlar[®], Kevlar[®] 129, and Twaron[®] single fibers increase only by 8%, 8%, and 6%, respectively, as the strain rate increases over 6 decades.

2.4 Transverse Compression Tests

In many applications, the high-performance fibers are compressed in the in the transverse direction, the load then spread in the form of axial tension. It is thus important to know the axial strength of the fibers after being compressed laterally. In the experiments described here, single PPTA fiber was compressed transversely using a transverse test system, and then pulled using the miniaturized tension bar. Fig. 4 shows the schematic diagram for measurement of the force and displacement applied

Fig.4. Schematic diagram of transverse test system

to a single fiber transversely. The system includes a piezoelectric translator (Physik Instrument LVPZT, P840.20) traveling up to $30\ \mu\text{m}$, push and supporting rods, and a precision vertical translation stage for the proper positioning and alignment. Transverse compressive load is measured directly by a low profile load cell with a capacity of 22.24 N (5lbf). The corresponding displacement is measured by a capacitive displacement sensor with sub-nanometer resolution. Single PPTA fiber was compressed transversely at a strain rate of 0.001/s to about 70~80% of the fiber diameter. Fig. 5(a) shows the typical transverse compressive response with two distinct transition points, similar to the transverse behavior reported previously on other fibers. The first transition point (marked A in Fig. 5(a)) separates linear and nonlinear behaviors at a nominal strain of 15-20% (nominal strain is defined as the displacement of the bottom surface of the push rod divided by the diameter of the fiber).

Fig 5. Transverse compressive stress-strain curve showing ductile behaviour of single Kevlar® fiber in one cycle of loading and unloading (a) and deformed shape (b).

From this point, the single PPTA fiber begins to yield inducing large residual strain in the fiber. The second transition point (marked B in Fig. 5(a)) arises at a nominal strain of about 40% in which transverse force increases sharply. After one cycle of loading and unloading, a large residual strain (~52% nominal strain) remains in the fiber as shown in Fig. 5(a). Fig. 5(b) presents the high resolution SEM image showing the deformed Kevlar® single fiber after transverse compression. In order to investigate the effect of the transverse compression on the tensile behavior of the fiber at high strain rate, single PPTA fiber was compressed transversely up to about 80% of the fiber diameter and then pulled at the high strain rate of 1500/s. These experimental results show that the tensile strengths of Kevlar®, Kevlar® 129, and Twaron® single fibers decrease only by 10.8%, 11.4%, and 6.3%, respectively, due to the damage in the fibers from large transverse deformation. This is a critical feature of high-performance fibers. The high residual axial tensile strength indicates the strong capacity of these fibers to spread impact loads.

3 Conclusions

The mechanical behavior of three high-performance PPTA single fibers (Kevlar®, Kevlar® 129, and Twaron®) was studied at both quasi-static and high strain rates. From the quasi-static experiments at six different gage lengths, no significant gage length effect on the tensile strengths of Kevlar® and Twaron® single fibers was observed. A miniature tension Kolsky bar was modified to conduct high-rate tension experiments. Experimental results at strain rates from $\dot{\epsilon} = 0.001\text{s}^{-1}$ to $\dot{\epsilon} \approx 1500\text{s}^{-1}$ showed that the tensile strengths of these PPTA single fibers do not exhibit significant strain-rate effects. The high resolution SEM images showing a fibrillated end of Kevlar® single fiber at both quasi-static and high strain rate also indicate that the longitudinal failure behavior of these PPTA single fibers does not vary significantly in this strain-rate range. The experimental results also show that the direction of a fiber in the woven fabric does not affect the tensile strength significantly, although the fibers from the fill direction are slightly stronger. Transverse compression effect on the axial strengths of the PPTA single fibers at the high strain rate was

investigated using a transverse test system and then the miniaturized tension Kolsky bar. The axial strengths of the PPTA single fibers after being compressed laterally were measured. Experimental results showing a small reduction in their tensile strength indicate the strong capacity of these fibers to spread impact loads from transverse directions.

References

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